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Performing Gender on the Early Modern Stage: a Computational and Cross-lingual Approach to Male and Female Speech in European drama

Early modern drama offers a unique showcase of Judith Butler's influential theory that gender roles are performed rather than embodied (Butler 1990). Because women were not allowed to act in German, Dutch and English theatres until the second half of the seventeenth century, female roles were mostly played by male actors. Even after actresses entered the stage, male acting remained the norm for decades. The situation was different in Spanish and Italian theatres, where women had been acting since the sixteenth century, but that did not mean that the performance of gender roles conformed to a strictly binary norm in Southern Europe. Through narrative devices such as cross-dressing, masks and other disguises, maleness and femaleness were repeatedly constructed and deconstructed in dramatic story worlds from the Iberian and Italian peninsulas. As a result, in early modern European drama gender was often not a stable character trait, but a flexible feature that had to be performed in an interaction between actors, characters and the audience.

In earlier work (Van der Deijl and Lassche, forthcoming), we analysed the relationship between gender and character speech in early modern Dutch plays by classifying the gender of the characters in the corpus based on the gendered patterns in their language, using large language models (LLMs). By evaluating the error rate of our classifications, the distinctiveness of 'male' versus 'female' speech could be assessed in that corpus. In this paper, we build on that work by exploring to what extent multilingual LLMs can be used to make a comparison across multiple languages. The central questions of this study are (1) whether we can, given the speech text of a certain character, predict the gender of that character, and (2) how we can explain differences in accuracy of the gender predictions based on character speech in the studied languages.

We compare the construction of gender roles in 2501 early modern plays first printed between 1500 and 1800 and written within dramatic traditions from six European language fields: French, German, English, Spanish, Dutch and Italian. We aim to analyse the relationship between gender and character speech by classifying the gender of 33,250 characters, using both monolingual and multilingual large language models (LLMs). This would enable us to make a cross-lingual, historical comparison of gender distinctions and gender performance in European drama.

Previous work

In computational literary studies, text classification has often been applied to analyse distinctions between gender categories in literary texts. Using a similar methodology to classify gender based on labelled datasets for 'male' and 'female' samples, previous computational studies of gendered character descriptions from modern and contemporary English novels (cf. Jockers 2019; Underwood et al. 2018) or modern Dutch novels (Vitse 2024; cf. Smeets 2024) produced high accuracy scores. Šeja et al. (2023) also found a gender effect on the character distinctiveness of male and female speech in four corpora of early modern plays. High performance of those classification tasks can be interpreted as computational evidence of clear distinctions between male and female character descriptions in the studied genre and period. These studies indicate that character gender is often associated with specific gendered registers in novels and possibly also in plays.

Data

The corpus was extracted from the largest six corpora of the international theatre database developed by the Drama Corpora Project (DraCor). DraCor is an infrastructure and ‘programmable corpus’ that facilitates computational and cross-lingual comparisons between multiple digital theatre editions, by standardising the xml-encoding of its editions (based on the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI)) and by creating multiple entry points into the data, both through the project’s website and its API (Fischer et al. 2019). All plays first published between 1500 and 1800 were selected for analysis. DraCor’s encoding standards – which for example require gender labels for all speakers and unique speaker IDs for all speech turns in a play – enabled a systematic extraction of all male and female speech text in the selected plays.¹ This extraction resulted in the dataset described in Table 1. Figure 1 shows the total proportion of male and female speech turns and characters in each corpus. The proportions do not sum up to 100 % because characters without a gender label have been omitted.

Corpus (language)	Plays	Speech turns	Characters
FreDraCor (French)	1343	399,440	13,718
EngDraCor (English)	434	310,920	7124
GerDraCor (German)	225	124,141	3285
CalDraCor (Spanish)	205	121,382	5916
DutchDraCor (Dutch)	180	60,021	2122
ItaDraCor (Italian)	114	62,992	1085
Total	2501	1,078,896	33,250

Table 1. Corpus characteristics.

Figure 1. Proportions of male and female speech turns and characters per corpus.

¹ Please note that the quality of the annotation differs per corpus. For example, in some corpora, there is a substantial number of characters without a gender label. We only included character speech from characters that had been enriched with a gender label ‘male’ or ‘female’.

Methodology

The design of our methodology is borrowed from our previous study of gendered speech in early modern Dutch plays (Van der Deijl and Lassche; forthcoming). The study proposed in this abstract expands on the findings from our previous work on Dutch drama, and explores to what extent multilingual models can play a meaningful role in offering a transnational and trans-historical approach to gender distinctions in European drama at large.

We propose the following methodological pipeline for each corpus:

1. **Clustering task for model selection.** This task consists of two parts. In part one, we take for every language a fixed number (40) of characters with the most speech text, and chunk their speech text in fragments of equal length, experimenting with chunk sizes of 200, 300, and 400 tokens. We test multiple multilingual LLMs, create embeddings of the fragments, and apply K-means clustering to see with which embeddings best cluster the text fragments of each character. The performance is measured using the V-score. In part two, we continue with the best chunk size (400 tokens) and the three best performing models, this time varying the number of characters. We experiment with selecting the top 10, 20, 30, and 40 speakers. We perform the same clustering task, this time with sampling over 20 iterations. The sample sizes are 150, 300, 450, and 600. We interpret the performances of these tasks as an indicator of how well a model is able to encode the semantic and stylistic features of that corpus and language. We continue with the best performing multilingual model (see Table 2 for the used models, see Appendix C for the performance metrics).
2. **Preparing the data.** We take each corpus as a whole and group all male and female speech turns together and segment them into equally sized fragments. We create a balanced dataset, meaning there are as many speech texts by male speakers as female speakers. We divide each selection of fragments into a training and test set (80/20).
3. **Performing a baseline experiment.** We use the TfidfVectorizer from the Python package scikit-learn is used to transform the text data, using range (2,3), and a LogisticRegression model is trained on the training set across 50 iterations. The trained model is then used to make predictions on the test set. The F1-score of this experiment functions as a baseline to the other experiments with LLMs.
4. **Performing LLM experiments.** Our text fragments are tokenized and encoded using the jina-embeddings-v3 model to generate contextual embeddings. These embeddings are then used as input features for a LogisticRegression model, which is trained on the training set across 50 iterations. As in step 3, the trained classifier is used to make predictions on the test set, enabling a direct comparison of model performance across representations.
5. **Comparing classification performances across languages.** The F1-score of every model indicates the reliability of the classification and can be interpreted as a metric for the distinctiveness of the attributed classes ('male' versus 'female'). A high F1-score indicates a strong difference between male and female speech, whereas a low F1-score indicates a strong similarity between male and female speech. We compare F1-scores of the same model between languages, and we discuss to what extent these comparisons can give us insight into differences in gendered speech per language of European drama.

Multilingual model	Source
xlm-roberta-large (Conneau et al. 2020)	https://huggingface.co/FacebookAI/xlm-roberta-large
multilingual-e5-large (Wang et al. 2024)	https://huggingface.co/intfloat/multilingual-e5-large
t5-large (Raffel et al. 2020)	https://huggingface.co/google-t5/t5-large
jina-embeddings-v3 (Sturua et al. 2024)	https://huggingface.co/jinaai/jina-embeddings-v3

Table 2. Selection of multilingual Transformer models.

Results and relevance

In this paper we report three types of results:

1. Descriptive statistics about the visibility of male and female characters in each corpus in terms of characters and characters speech (cf. Appendix A & B).
2. Accuracy scores (F1) of the gender classifications from our baseline experiment based on TF-IDF (cf. Appendix D).
3. Accuracy scores (F1) of the gender classifications based on the LLM experiments (cf. Appendix D).

The descriptive statistics and the accuracy scores allow us to evaluate the performance of the multilingual models for the classification of gendered speech from early modern drama in the studied languages. Taking into account the limits and biases of the used models, we interpret the error rate in each corpus as an indication of the differences in gender distinctions and gender performances between six different literary traditions. Our study thus seeks to explore both the potential and limitations of using multilingual models for cross-lingual comparisons between literary corpora. We furthermore hope that this work can contribute to the development of new, transnational historiographies of gender performativity in early modern Europe.

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APPENDIX A: FEMALE VISIBILITY AND HEARABILITY

Figure 2: Distributions of percentages of female characters and lines per play, by corpus.

APPENDIX B: MALE VISIBILITY AND HEARABILITY

Figure 3: Distributions of percentages of male characters and lines per play, by corpus.

APPENDIX C: PERFORMANCE METRICS OF CLUSTERING TASKS FOR MODEL SELECTION

Corpus →	fre			eng			ger			cal			dutch			ita		
Chunk size →																		
Model ↓	200	300	400	200	300	400	200	300	400	200	300	400	200	300	400	200	300	400
xlm-roberta-large	0,152	0,190	0,197	0,576	0,685	0,697	0,474	0,538	0,543	0,199	0,232	0,265	0,570	0,605	0,607	0,520	0,579	0,582
m-e5-large	0,194	0,236	0,247	0,517	0,619	0,600	0,526	0,570	0,597	0,287	0,336	0,352	0,630	0,673	0,635	0,589	0,643	0,640
t5-large	0,156	0,186	0,209	0,622	0,730	0,754	0,469	0,534	0,568	0,180	0,225	0,265	0,540	0,598	0,654	0,482	0,549	0,594
jina-embeddings-v3	0,204	0,243	0,264	0,488	0,614	0,638	0,470	0,528	0,584	0,284	0,328	0,353	0,569	0,628	0,670	0,569	0,599	0,653

Table 3. Performance metrics of clustering tasks with text chunks of varying length of the 40 largest speakers in every language.

Corpus →	fre				eng				ger				cal				dutch				ita			
Sample size →	150	300	450	600	150	300	450	600	150	300	450	600	150	300	450	600	150	300	450	600	150	300	450	600
Top speakers →	10	20	30	40	10	20	30	40	10	20	30	40	10	20	30	40	10	20	30	40	10	20	30	40
m-e5-large	0,279	0,304	0,343	0,371	0,737	0,641	0,633	0,601	0,467	0,526	0,542	0,560	0,342	0,364	0,388	0,415	0,582	0,599	0,616	0,645	0,619	0,612	0,619	0,633
t5-large	0,277	0,307	0,344	0,370	0,866	0,793	0,783	0,757	0,499	0,561	0,577	0,591	0,278	0,306	0,340	0,368	0,562	0,603	0,611	0,647	0,591	0,571	0,590	0,597

jina-embeddings-v3	0,295	0,328	0,373	0,401	0,823	0,684	0,671	0,652	0,451	0,515	0,526	0,562	0,365	0,386	0,415	0,428	0,587	0,626	0,633	0,661	0,637	0,625	0,635	0,647
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Table 4. Performance metrics of clustering tasks with a varying sample size of chunks (length = 400 tokens) of the top speakers in every language. We experiment with the top 10, 20, 30, and 40 speakers, using a sample size based on the smallest corpus. Sampling is done over 20 iterations.

APPENDIX D: PERFORMANCE METRICS OF CLASSIFICATION TASKS

Corpus	fre				eng				ger				cal				dutch				ita			
Features	TF/IDF		embs																					
	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀
P	0,701	0,715	0,677	0,662	0,711	0,735	0,697	0,687	0,77	0,807	0,696	0,687	0,771	0,809	0,675	0,67	0,762	0,793	0,651	0,656	0,848	0,914	0,752	0,724
R	0,724	0,69	0,648	0,691	0,748	0,696	0,679	0,704	0,818	0,754	0,678	0,704	0,821	0,755	0,664	0,68	0,804	0,748	0,661	0,645	0,921	0,834	0,708	0,766
F1	0,713	0,702	0,662	0,676	0,729	0,714	0,688	0,695	0,793	0,779	0,687	0,695	0,795	0,781	0,669	0,674	0,782	0,769	0,656	0,65	0,883	0,872	0,729	0,744

Table 5. Performance metrics per gender class of classification tasks using a LogisticRegression model with TF/IDF as features, and with jina embeddings as features.